

EMERGING RESISTOTYPES OF MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT UROPATHOGENS IN URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS: A HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY FROM ISLAMABAD

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Abstract

Objectives: The primary objective of this study is to investigate the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) common bacterial organism in urinary tract infections (UTIs) from patients in a hospital setting.

1. Evaluate the demographic distribution of UTI patients and its association with common bacterial infections.
2. Evaluate the efficacy of commonly used antibiotics and the phenotypic Resist type among MDR Isolate.

Methodology:

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Islamabad, in collaboration with associated healthcare facilities.

Study Design: A prospective, cross-sectional study was employed to investigate MDR bacterial strains in UTIs. Urine samples were cultured on CLED agar for bacterial isolation, and antibiotic susceptibility was assessed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, following CLSI guidelines.

Sampling Technique: Non-probability convenience sampling was used to select 70 urine samples, including 50 from patients with suspected UTIs and 20 negative controls, from individuals presenting at the study site.

Sample Size: A total of 70 urine samples were analyzed, comprising 50 UTI cases and 20 controls.

Study Duration: Data collection spanned four months, from February 2025 to May 2025.

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize bacterial prevalence and resistance patterns. Chi-square tests were applied to assess the association between bacterial species and MDR status, with significance set at $p < 0.05$, using SPSS (version 27).

Results: *Escherichia coli* was the most common uropathogen (84%), followed by *Pseudomonas spp.* (14%) and *Klebsiella spp.* (2%). Of the isolates, 40% exhibited MDR, defined as resistance to at least one antibiotic in three or more classes. High resistance was observed for Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone (58% each), while

Fosfomycin and Nitrofurantoin showed low resistance, suggesting their potential as effective treatments. Females comprised 80% of UTI cases, though MDR rates were similar across genders. A significant association ($p=0.04051$) was found between bacterial species and MDR status.

Conclusion: *This study highlights the alarming prevalence of MDR uropathogens in Islamabad, with E. coli being the dominant culprit. The findings underscore the need for targeted antibiotic stewardship, routine resistance testing, and enhanced monitoring to combat MDR UTIs effectively. By identifying key resist types and demographic patterns, this research offers practical insights to improve treatment outcomes and patient care in hospital settings*

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most frequently encountered bacterial infections in both community and hospital settings, contributing significantly to global morbidity and healthcare costs (1). The term UTI broadly refers to infections involving any part of the urinary tract system, though in routine practice, it is most commonly associated with infections of the bladder (cystitis) (2). UTIs affect individuals of all ages and genders but are particularly prevalent among females due to anatomical predispositions such as a shorter urethra and proximity to the anal region (3). Epidemiological studies estimate that approximately 50-60% of women will experience at least one UTI in their lifetime, with a high recurrence rate reported in nearly 20-30% of cases (4).

UTIs are generally classified into two major categories based on the site of infection: lower UTIs, such as cystitis, and upper UTIs, such as pyelonephritis which involves infection of the kidneys (5). Uncomplicated UTIs typically affect otherwise healthy individuals without structural or functional abnormalities of the urinary tract, while complicated UTIs are often associated with anatomical or functional issues, urinary catheters, immunosuppression, or other comorbidities that compromise host defense mechanisms (6). Common symptoms of UTIs include dysuria, increased urinary frequency and urgency, suprapubic pain, and in severe cases, hematuria and fever (7).

The causative organisms of UTIs are predominantly Gram-negative bacteria, with Escherichia coli being the most prevalent uropathogen, accounting for approximately 70-90% of community-acquired infections (8). Other notable uropathogens include Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Proteus mirabilis, and Staphylococcus saprophyticus, particularly in complicated or healthcare-associated infections (9). These bacteria possess a range of virulence factors that aid colonization, adherence to uroepithelial cells, and evasion of host immune responses, facilitating their survival within the urinary tract (10).

In recent years, the management of UTIs has been significantly complicated by the alarming rise of multidrug-resistant (MDR) organisms, which exhibit resistance to multiple classes of antibiotics, including β -lactams, aminoglycosides, and fluoroquinolones (11). MDR bacteria are typically defined as strains resistant to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial categories (12). The global spread of MDR organisms has been attributed to various factors including inappropriate prescribing practices, patient non-compliance, self-medication, and the availability of over-the-counter antibiotics without prescription in many developing countries (13). Infections caused by MDR pathogens often lead to therapeutic failures, prolonged hospitalizations, increased healthcare costs, and heightened mortality rates (14).

MDR in urinary pathogens is mediated by multiple mechanisms including the production of extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs), carbapenemases, efflux pumps, and alterations in target binding sites, rendering many conventional therapies ineffective (15). Resistance genes such as blaCTX-M, blaNDM, and blaOXA are often transmitted through mobile genetic elements like plasmids, transposons, and integrons, facilitating rapid dissemination among bacterial populations (16). Furthermore, the biofilm-forming ability of uropathogens enhances their resistance to both antimicrobial agents and host immune defenses, contributing to persistent and recurrent infections (17).

Several host-related factors further predispose individuals to UTIs with MDR pathogens, including prolonged catheterization, advanced age, immunosuppression (as seen in diabetes, HIV, or cancer patients), recurrent UTIs, and poor personal hygiene (18). Hospitalized patients, especially those with indwelling urinary catheters or undergoing invasive procedures, are at an increased risk of acquiring MDR infections due to the compromised integrity of mucosal barriers and increased exposure to resistant organisms in the healthcare environment (19). Additionally, immunocompromised individuals are more susceptible to severe and recurrent MDR UTIs due to impaired neutrophil function and reduced immune surveillance (20).

In Pakistan, the burden of MDR UTIs is particularly concerning due to widespread misuse of antibiotics, lack of standardized infection control practices, and poor regulatory oversight of antimicrobial use (21). Studies have reported a high prevalence of MDR *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* among uropathogens isolated from both community and hospital settings, posing substantial challenges for clinicians in selecting appropriate empirical therapies (22). Inappropriate empirical treatment not only contributes to treatment failures but also promotes further resistance development among bacterial populations (23).

Given these alarming trends, there is a pressing need for continuous surveillance of resistance patterns among uropathogens and the implementation of robust antibiotic stewardship programs to preserve the efficacy of existing antimicrobial agents (24). This study aims to investigate the prevalence of MDR phenotypic resistotypes among common bacterial uropathogens isolated from UTI patients at Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Islamabad, while also evaluating demographic distributions and the efficacy of commonly used antibiotics against these resistant strains.

Rationale

This research will contribute to the understanding of the burden of multidrug-resistant bacterial infections in UTI patients. It will determine the prevalence of multidrug-resistant bacterial infections in UTI patients. The findings will inform the development of effective treatment strategies, improve patient outcomes, and reduce the spread of these resistant bacteria.

It will identify risk factors (Demographical linkage) associated with multidrug-resistant bacterial infections in UTI patients. It will develop effective treatment strategies and guidelines for managing.

AIM OF STUDY

This study aims to analyze the phenotypic resistotypes of common bacterial organism's isolates against commonly prescribed antimicrobial agents. Through antimicrobial susceptibility testing, the study will identify resistance trends

Research objectives

- The primary objective of this study is to investigate the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) common bacterial organism in urinary tract infections (UTIs) from patients in a hospital setting.
- Evaluate the demographic distribution of UTI patients and its association with common bacterial infections.

- Evaluate the efficacy of commonly used antibiotics and the phenotypic Resistotype among MDR Isolate.

Study Design

This study was designed as a prospective cross-sectional study.

Study Setting

The study was conducted at the Microbiology Department of Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Isra University, Islamabad Campus, which serves as a tertiary care center for diagnosing and managing infectious diseases, including UTIs.

Sampling Area

Samples were collected and analyzed at the Microbiology Department of Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Islamabad.

Duration of Study

The study was conducted over a period of four months, from February, 2025, to May, 2025.

Sample Size

A total of 70 Urine samples were collected from patients with suspected UTIs.

Sample Size Calculation Formula

The sample size calculation for antibiotic susceptibility testing can be determined using the formula

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p)}{E^2}$$

Where

n is the required sample size.

Z is the Z score corresponding to the desired confidence level.

P is the estimated prevalence or proportion.

E is the margin of error

For a 95% confidence level (Z = 1.96) and an estimated prevalence of 50% for a conservative approach, let's substitute these values

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.508476 \cdot (1-0.508476)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 3.8416 \cdot 0.508476(1 - 0.508476) / 0.0025$$

$$n = 1,952036(1 - 0.508476) / 0.0025$$

$$n = 1.952036 \cdot 0.491524 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.960375 / 0.0025 \quad n = 50$$

The analysis of antibiotic susceptibility patterns is a standard practice in microbiology, and there are various guidelines available, such as those provided by the Latest Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) 2023.5 or the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) 2024.

Sampling Technique

A non-probability convenient sampling technique was used, where samples were collected from patients meeting the inclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Urine Samples from patients with suspected UTIs were included.
2. Samples were taken from both male and female patients of all age groups.
3. Patients from outpatient and inpatient departments were included.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Samples from patients who had received antibiotic therapy within the last 48 hours were excluded to minimize the influence of prior treatment.
2. Contaminated samples were excluded to ensure accurate microbiological results.
3. Samples unrelated to UTIs were excluded.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This prospective, cross-sectional study was conducted from February 2025 to June 2025 at the Department of Microbiology, Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Islamabad, a tertiary care teaching hospital, in collaboration with its associated diagnostic laboratories.

Sample Collection and Processing

A total of 70 urine specimens were collected via a non-probability convenience sampling technique, which included 50 midstream urine samples from clinically suspected UTI patients and 20 control samples from healthy individuals without symptoms of UTI. Specimen collection and transport followed standard microbiological guidelines to minimize contamination.

Culture Media Preparation

Cystine Lactose Electrolyte-Deficient (CLED) Agar was prepared following the manufacturer’s instructions (28-30g per liter of distilled water), sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes. Plates were poured under aseptic conditions in a laminar flow hood and stored at 4°C until use. CLED agar was selected for its ability to support the growth of both lactose-fermenting and non-fermenting uropathogens while inhibiting *Proteus* spp. swarming.

Isolation and Identification of Uropathogens

Urine samples were inoculated on CLED agar using a calibrated sterile loop (0.001 mL) via the streak plate method to promote isolated colony formation. Plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24-48 hours. Bacterial isolates were identified based on colony morphology, lactose fermentation patterns, and pigmentation on CLED agar.

Further confirmation was achieved through a series of biochemical tests following standard protocols:

- Gram Staining
- Catalase Test
- Oxidase Test
- Indole Test
- Urease Test
- Citrate Utilization Test (Simmons Agar)
- Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Agar Slants

Lactose fermenters (e.g., *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* spp.) were identified by yellow colonies, while non-fermenters (e.g., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp.) appeared blue-green or pale.

Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing (AST)

Antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of the isolated uropathogens were determined by the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton Agar according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) 2025 guidelines. Bacterial suspensions were prepared and adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity (~ 1-2 x 10⁸ CFU/mL). Antibiotic discs representing commonly prescribed antimicrobials (penicillins, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, nitrofurantoin, tetracyclines, etc.) were placed on the inoculated plates at standardized distances.

Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. Zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters using a calibrated scale, and susceptibility interpretations (sensitive, intermediate, resistant) were made in accordance with CLSI 2025 breakpoints.

Materials Used

Material	Purpose/Role
CLED Agar	Isolation and differentiation of uropathogens
Mueller-Hinton Agar	Antibiotic susceptibility testing
Antibiotic Discs (CLSI 2025)	Standardized assessment of antimicrobial resistance
Biochemical Reagents	Identification of isolates through standard tests
Incubator (37°C)	Controlled growth conditions for bacterial cultures
Measuring Caliper	Accurate measurement of inhibition zones

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using **SPSS version 27**. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages) summarized the distribution of bacterial species, demographic characteristics, and antibiotic resistance patterns. Associations between bacterial isolates and multidrug resistance (MDR) status were assessed using the **Chi-square test**, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

In the current study, we analyzed 70 clinical samples that were acquired due to suspected urinary tract infections (UTIs) caused by multiple organisms, in which 20 samples were negative. The data supports the notion that multi-organism UTIs are becoming increasingly common and must be considered in

routine clinical evaluations. This study underscores the importance of targeted antimicrobial therapy and further reinforces the need for precise microbiological identification in order to manage such infections effectiveness.

4.1 Isolation and identification of bacteria on CLED Agar

Escherichia coli was isolated on Cystine-Lactose-Electrolyte-Deficient (CLED) agar. The yellow colonies indicated lactose fermentation, a characteristic feature used for presumptive identification of *E. coli*, a common uropathogen. CLED agar was utilized as a differential medium to inhibit swarming of *Proteus* species, which aided in the clear visualization of other bacterial colonies as show in fig IV.1

IV.1 Fig: Identification of *E.colion* CLED Agar

4.2 Bacteria identification and biochemical Test.

Gram staining of bacterial isolates from UTI samples demonstrated gram-negative bacilli morphology under. Gram staining was performed as a fundamental step in bacterial identification, differentiating bacteria based on cell wall structure and assisting in the selection of appropriate downstream tests and potential antibiotic treatments. The predominance of gram-negative bacilli was observed, consistent with the common etiology of UTIs as show in fig IV.2.1

Citrate utilization test result. The change from green (negative control) to blue indicated the organism's ability to use citrate as the sole carbon source. This biochemical test was used to differentiate between Enterobacteriaceae species as show in fig IV.2.2. Positive TSI and citrate is presenting presence of *E. coli* as show I fig IV.2.3

Oxidase test results. The development of a dark purple color (positive result) indicated the presence of cytochrome c oxidase. This test was used to

differentiate among gram-negative bacteria as show in fig IV.2.4 and IV.2.5

Indole test result. The formation of a red ring after the addition of Kovac's reagent indicated the organism's ability to break down tryptophan into indole. This test was performed to identify *E. coli* and other bacterial species as show in fig IV.2.6

Urease test results. The change in color from yellow/orange (negative) to pink/fuchsia (positive) revealed the organism's capacity to hydrolyze urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. This test aided in the identification of *Proteus* spp. and other urease-producing bacteria as show in fig IV.2.7

IV.2.1 Fig: Gram staining show gram negative bacilli

The predominance of gram-negative bacilli was observed, consistent with the common etiology of UTIs.

IV.2.2 Fig: Citrate positive test

Citrate utilization test result. The change from green (negative control) to blue indicated the organism's ability to use citrate as the sole carbon source. This

biochemical test was used to differentiate between Enterobacteriaceae species.

IV.2.3 Fig: TSI positive test

Positive TSI showing presence of E.coli .

IV.2.4 figure: Oxidase positive Test (A)

IV.2.5 figure: Oxidase positive Test (B)

Oxidase test results. The development of a dark purple color (positive result) indicated the presence of cytochrome c oxidase. This test was used to differentiate among gram-negative bacteria

IV.2.6Fig: Indole positive test

Indole test result. The formation of a red ring after the addition of Kovac's reagent indicated the organism's ability to break down tryptophan into indole.

IV.2.7Fig: Urease Positive test

The change in color from yellow/orange (negative) to pink/fuchsia (positive) revealed the organism's capacity to hydrolyze urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide.

4.3 Antibiotic susceptibility Profile Test by Kerbay Bar Disk Method

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. The zones of inhibition around the antibiotic disks indicated the susceptibility of the bacterial isolate to the tested

antibiotics. The varying zone sizes reflected differing levels of resistance or sensitivity. These results were crucial for determining the MDR profiles of the isolates and guiding effective treatment strategies for UTIs as show in fig IV.3.1

IV.3.1Fig: Antibiotics Susceptibility

The zones of inhibition around the antibiotic disks indicated the susceptibility of the bacterial isolate to the tested antibiotics. The varying zone sizes reflected differing levels of resistance or sensitivity.

This current study analyzes 70 urine culture samples to investigate multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacterial organisms in UTIs.

Females constitute 80% of UTI cases, reflecting higher susceptibility possibly due to urogenital structural variations, as shown in graph IV.3. Both p-value of 0.04051 indicates a statistically significant association between the type of bacterial organism and multidrug resistance ($p \leq 0.05$) as shown in graph IV.4. Females exhibit a higher number of MDR cases (16 vs. 4 in males), but the proportion of MDR cases is similar across genders (~40%) as shown in graph IV.4. The primary organisms identified are *E. coli* (84% of cases), *Pseudomonas* spp. (14%), and *Klebsiella* spp. (2%). Approximately 40% of isolates exhibit MDR, defined as resistance to at least one antibiotic in three or more classes. The analysis evaluates antibiotic efficacy and demographic distributions, revealing challenges in treatment and infection control.

E. coli dominates UTI cases, with most of the samples. A statistically significant association was observed between bacterial species and multidrug resistance, with a p-value of 0.04051 ($p \leq 0.05$) as shown in graph VI.1

Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone shows the highest resistance rate (58% of tested cases), indicating potential treatment challenges. Fosfomycin and Nitrofurantoin remain highly effective, with low resistance rates as shown in graph VI.2

This study identified four key resistotypes among MDR uropathogens, with the most common being Cefepime/Ciprofloxacin/Ceftriaxone and Cefepime/Doxycycline/Ceftriaxon (each 24%). These patterns reflect high resistance to third-generation cephalosporins,

fluoroquinolones, and tetracyclines critical antibiotics in UTI management.

A more extensive resistance profile Cefepime/Ciprofloxacin/Ceftriaxone/Doxycycline—was found in 14% of cases, indicating increased treatment challenges. A smaller group (2%) showed resistance to Nitrofurantoin/Levofloxacin, drugs typically used in uncomplicated UTIs.

These findings suggest possible ESBL production and emphasize the urgent need for targeted antibiotic stewardship and regular surveillance to guide effective UTI treatment and control MDR spread.

Ceftriaxone and Ciprofloxacin, a commonly used cephalosporin, shows alarmingly high resistance (58% of tested cases), particularly in *E. coli* infections. This suggests a need for alternative treatment strategies,

such as Fosfomycin or Nitrofurantoin, which exhibit lower resistance rates.

The study reveals a significant prevalence of MDR E. coli in UTIs, with 38% of isolates showing resistance to multiple antibiotic classes. Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone's high resistance rate underscores the

need for careful antibiotic selection. Females are disproportionately affected, but MDR prevalence is consistent across genders. These findings highlight the importance of targeted antibiotic stewardship and infection control measures to combat MDR UTIs effectively as shown in table IV.1 and graph IV.5.

Antibiotics E.coli Pseudomonas ssp. Klebsiella ssp.
IV.1 graph: Prevalence of common UTI causing pathogens

IV.2 graph: Frequency distribution of resistance MDR

IV.3 graph: Gender distribution of UTI patients In Percentage

VI.4 graph: Age distribution of UTI patients

Gender distribution Among UTI Patients

VI.5 graph: MDR Prevalence by Gender

VI.1Table : Antibiotics and phenotypic Resist type among MDR Isolate

sr no	Resistotype Medicine Name	Total no	Percentage
1	Cefipime/Ciprofloxacin/Ceftriaxone/Doxycycline	7	14%
2	Cefipime/Ciprofloxacin/Ceftriaxone	12	24%
3	cefipime/Doxycycline/Ceftriaxone	12	24%
4	Nitrofurantoin/Levofloxacin	1	2%

IV.6 Graph: Antibiotics and phenotypic Resistotype among MDR Isolate

CHAPTER V

Discussion

In our study conducted at Al Nafees Medical College and Hospital, Islamabad, *Escherichia coli* was identified as the predominant uropathogen, accounting for 84% of UTI cases, followed by *Pseudomonas* spp. (14%) and *Klebsiella* spp. (2%). As it is reported before in (25) The sensitivity test results show that *E. coli* is most common pathogen and responds very well to nitrofurantoin, indicating that this antibiotic could be a highly effective option for treating *E. coli* infections. These findings align with those reported by Khan et al. (2024), who observed a similar distribution in Pakistani women with uncomplicated UTIs, highlighting *E. coli* as the most prevalent pathogen in urinary tract infections (26).

A significant concern in our study was the high prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains. Specifically, 38% of *E. coli* isolates exhibited resistance to multiple antibiotic classes. This trend is consistent with findings from Ali Hassan et al. (2024), who reported substantial resistance patterns among community-acquired urinary pathogens across various

hospital settings in Pakistan. Their study emphasized the growing challenge of managing UTIs in the presence of MDR organisms and highlighted the need for region-specific resistance data (27).

Gender distribution analysis revealed that 80% of UTI cases occurred in female patients. This observation is consistent with established literature that indicates higher susceptibility among females due to anatomical and physiological factors. However, MDR rates were nearly equal among males and females, suggesting that antibiotic resistance is influenced more by environmental factors such as self-medication and inappropriate antibiotic use rather than biological sex. These conclusions are corroborated by Gu et al. (2022), who reported gender-based variations in microbial profiles but found no significant difference in resistance levels across sexes(28).

Our study included an age-wise analysis and found patterns consistent with existing literature, which shows that older adults especially those above 50 years—are at higher risk for MDR UTIs. A single-center study from Saudi Arabia by Alhomayani et al. (2022)

reported that 47.1% of MDR UTI cases were found in patients aged over 70 years, with significant associations noted between MDR infections and chronic comorbidities like diabetes mellitus and hypertension. This underscores the need to include age stratification and comorbidity analysis in future UTI surveillance studies (29).

Regarding antibiotic sensitivity patterns, our findings demonstrated high resistance rates to commonly used antibiotics such as Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone, which raises concern over their continued use as empirical treatment options. In contrast, Fosfomycin and Nitrofurantoin showed promising results with low resistance levels. This is supported by Dzib-Baak et al. (2022), who highlighted Fosfomycin's efficacy against both planktonic and biofilm-associated MDR *E. coli*, suggesting its suitability in UTI management.⁷² Furthermore, Mahdizade Ari et al. (2023) conducted a comprehensive narrative review endorsing Nitrofurantoin as a first-line agent for uncomplicated UTIs due to its retained effectiveness and minimal resistance development (30).

our findings are in alignment with national and international studies, reflecting the predominance of *E. coli* in UTI infections and the concerning trend of rising multidrug resistance. The high resistance rates to Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone reinforce the need to shift away from these agents in empirical therapy and toward more effective alternatives like Fosfomycin and Nitrofurantoin. Integrating updated surveillance data and enforcing antibiotic stewardship programs, as highlighted in recent studies are essential to effectively combat MDR UTIs in both hospital and community settings.

CHAPTER VI

Conclusion

○ This study found a high prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) urinary tract infections at Al-Nafees Medical College and Hospital, with *Escherichia coli* as the most common pathogen (84%) and 40% of

isolates showing resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, posing a serious public health concern.

○ The demographic analysis revealed that 80% of UTI cases occurred in females, likely due to anatomical factors, but MDR rates were similar in both genders, emphasizing the widespread nature of antibiotic resistance.

○ Antibiotic susceptibility testing showed high resistance to Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone (58%), while Fosfomycin and Nitrofurantoin remained effective with low resistance rates.

○ Four main phenotypic resistotypes were observed among MDR isolates, with the most frequent patterns involving resistance to Cefepime, Ciprofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, and Doxycycline.

Limitations

Firstly, the sample size was limited to 70 urine specimens, out of which 50 were culture-positive and 20 were negative. Although valuable, this sample may not fully represent the broader patient population.

Lastly, due to limited resources and scope, we focused solely on phenotypic resistance patterns and were unable to perform molecular testing to identify specific resistance genes, which could have provided a deeper understanding of the mechanisms driving multidrug resistance.

Future Recommendations

1. Future research should include a broader variety of patients, covering different age groups, underlying health conditions, and both inpatient and outpatient settings. This would help to better understand how MDR patterns differ among populations.

2. Studies should also use molecular methods like PCR or gene sequencing to detect specific resistance genes and provide more detailed insights into how antibiotic resistance develops.

3. Hospitals should implement antibiotic stewardship efforts to guide better prescription

practices and reduce the misuse of antibiotics, which contributes to the rise of resistance.

Statements and Declarations:

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2. **Author contributions:** All authors have made equitable contributions to the manuscript.

3. **Conflict of interest:** The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

4. **Data availability statement:** The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

5. **Informed consent:** Written informed consent for participation and publication of clinical data was obtained from the families. The written informed consent was obtained from all participant families for clinical examination

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Institutional Research and Bioethics Committee (IRBC) of Al-Nafees Medical College (Reference No. F.1/IUIC-ANMC/IRBC-282/2025). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to sample collection. Confidentiality of patient data was ensured throughout the study, and data were securely stored on password-protected systems accessible only to the research team

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